

**D.4.1.3 Report on the survey
related to the quality and
accessibility of data used in
microbiological risk
assessment**
Workpackage 4

Responsible Partner: ANSES

Contributing partners: RIVM

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REPORT ON THE SURVEY RELATED TO THE AVAILABILITY AND QUALITY OF DATA USED FOR RISK ASSESSMENT

A. Survey on (publicly) accessible (meta-)data for risk assessment

1. Introduction to the survey

One of the objectives of Work Package 4 is to identify which (meta-) data is currently used in quantitative microbial risk assessment (QMRA) and meant to be shared.

A survey intended for OHEJP members and broader was launched from September 2020 to March 2021 to collect information about existing QMRA studies from 2015 to March 2021. The questionnaire was set up on Sphinx online software and was organized into 31 main questions divided into 3 sections. The first section corresponded to the identification of the respondent, followed by the description of the QMRA study and the data included. Questions about the existence of own databases and the willingness to publicly share the data were also included.

The details of the items on the questionnaire can be found in their entirety in Deliverable D.4.1.1 and in Appendix 1 of this document.

2. Contact list used for the dissemination of the survey

The list of the 51 contacts used for the dissemination of the survey is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Contact list

Country	Organization member	Contact	Mail
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B. Descriptive statistics of the survey results

1. Description of the survey participation

The survey was sent to 51 OH EJP members and broader, likely to conduct QMRA studies in September 2020. The survey ran for 7 months, until March 2021. Contacts who did not responded (n=49) have been re-launched once, in February 2021.

Ten contacts (20%) have completely filled the questionnaire from which, one declared to not perform any QMRA study. Nine other contacts reported that they did not perform QMRA over the past 5 years (2015 to march 2021) and did not filled the questionnaire. Consequently, 20 questionnaires were completely filled, one duplicate was detected (Quantification of the risk of human *Taenia solium* exposure from meat of home slaughtered pigs from RIVM) and one was out of scope (National Food and Veterinary Risk Assessment Institute from Lithuania). The studies taken into account are listed in Table 3.

The median time required to complete the questionnaire was 19 minutes (maximum : 156 minutes).

At the end, five organizations/institutions contributed to the survey: Anses, RIVM, University of Cordoba, Food Safety Authority of Ireland, BfR. In addition, a member of ANSES filled the survey considering EFSA microbiological risk assessment work.

2. Inventory of the QMRA reported in the survey

Eighteen QMRA studies carried out from six stakeholders were identified (Table 2 and Table 3) from 2015 to march 2021. The major contributor was Anses (n=8), followed by EFSA (n=4), RIVM (n=3) and University of Cordoba (n=2). Food Safety Authority of Ireland and BfR filled one QMRA each in the survey. One duplicate QMRA was observed from RIVM and only one single count was made from chapter 3.

Table 2: Number of QMRA studies per stakeholder reported in the survey

Organisation	Number of QMRAs
ANSES	8
University of Cordoba	2
RIVM	3*
Food Safety Authority of Ireland	1
BfR	1
EFSA	4
Total	18

*including one duplicate

The list of the QMRA studies is present in the table below:

Table 3: Title and acces to the QMRA studies included in the survey

Title of the study	URL/DOI	Organisation
Quantification of the risk of human <i>Taenia solium</i> exposure from meat of home slaughtered pigs	https://parasitesandvectors.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13071-019-3320-3	RIVM*
MDR bacteria in meat products	the work is on-going at this moment	University of Cordoba

Comparative exposure assessment of ESBL-producing Escherichia coli through meat consumption	https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0169589	RIVM
QMRA Taenia Solium	https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-019-3320-3	RIVM*
Opinion of the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety on the detection of shigatoxin-producing E. coli (STEC) considered highly pathogenic in the beef minced meat industry	https://www.anses.fr/fr/system/files/BIORISK2016SA0121.pdf	ANSES
Salmonella control measures in the pork meat industry: state of knowledge and quantitative risk assessment	https://www.anses.fr/fr/system/files/BIORISK2016SA0037Ra.pdf	ANSES
Closing gaps for performing a risk assessment on Listeria monocytogenes in ready-to-eat (RTE) foods: activity 2, a quantitative risk characterization on L. monocytogenes in RTE foods; starting from the retail stage	https://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2017.EN-1252	University of Cordoba
State of knowledge relating to the contamination of broilers with Campylobacter and assessment of the impact of interventions at different stages of the food chain in France	https://www.anses.fr/fr/system/files/BIORISK2016SA0183Ra.pdf	ANSES
Risk Ranking of Microbial hazards (currently in progress)		Food Safety Authority of Ireland
Opinion of the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety on the evaluation of protocols for the sampling of milk and cheese morbier and mont d'or in order to reduce the epidemic risk of salmonellosis	https://www.anses.fr/fr/system/files/BIORISK2016SA0168.pdf	ANSES
Opinion of the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety on the protocol for restarting the commercialization of reblochons cheese proposed by the company Chabert	https://www.anses.fr/fr/system/files/BIORISK2018SA0164.pdf	ANSES
Consumer information on the prevention of biological hazards associated with food Volume 2 - Evaluating the Effectiveness of Communication Strategies	https://www.anses.fr/fr/system/files/BIORISK2012sa0118Ra-02.pdf	ANSES

Opinion of the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety on consumer information on the prevention of microbiological risks related to food	https://www.anses.fr/fr/system/files/BIORISK2012sa0118Ra-02.pdf	ANSES
Opinion of the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety on consumer information on the prevention of microbiological risks related to food	https://www.anses.fr/fr/system/files/BIORISK2012sa0118Ra-02.pdf	ANSES
Salmonella in table eggs from farm to retail - When is cooling required?	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2014.07.018	BfR
Listeria monocytogenes contamination of ready-to-eat foods and the risk for human health in the EU	http://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2018.5134	EFSA
Evaluation of listeriosis risk related with the consumption of non-prepackaged ready-to-eat (RTE) cooked meat products handled at retail stores in Greece	http://doi.org/10.2903/sp.efsa.2019.EN-1677	EFSA
Update and review of control options for Campylobacter in broilers at primary production	http://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2020.6090	EFSA
The public health risk posed by Listeria monocytogenes in frozen fruit and vegetables including herbs, blanched during processing	https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2020.6092	EFSA

*Duplicates

3. Target population

3.1. Countries

The target population of the QMRA studies were mainly from European countries. Four QMRA studies were intended for the overall European population. Eight studies included the French population. One QMRA study included several target populations (Spain, Romania, Poland, Germany and Bulgaria). Also, the Dutch and Irish populations were the target country population in a study for each one (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Countries included in the QMRA studies reported in the survey

3.2. Ages class and immune status

The target population included in the microbiological risk assessment studies seems to be related to the type of hazard and not the type of food product.

When considering *Campylobacter* and *Salmonella* spp., general population were considered most of the time. Specific population were taken into account, when considering *Listeria* spp. (e.g. Infant or toddler; Adult; Elderly) and *E. coli* VTEC (e.g. children up to 14 years old) as indicated in Table 4. The population considered per QMRA study are indicated in the table below.

Table 4: Target population per QMRA study

Reference	Population	Hazard(s)	Food product
[1]	Children less than 4 years; Infant or toddler; Adult; Seniors; Teenagers	<i>Campylobacter</i>	Poultry
[2]	General population	<i>Campylobacter</i>	Poultry
[3]	General population	<i>Campylobacter</i>	Poultry
Food Safety Authority of Ireland (in progress)	General population	<i>Campylobacter</i> ; <i>Escherichia coli</i> , pathogenic, VTEC; Hepatitis E virus; <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> ; Norovirus (Norwalk-like virus); <i>Salmonella</i> ; <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	Unspecified
[4]	Children less than 4 years; Infant or toddler; Teenagers	Enterohemorrhagic <i>E. coli</i> (EHEC)	Beef
[5]	all humans of 2 years and older; no age categories were distinguished	ESBL-producing <i>Escherichia coli</i>	Beef, veal, pork, mutton/lamb, poultry
[2]	children under 15 years old	<i>Escherichia coli</i> VTEC, unspecified	Beef

University of Cordoba (in progress)	Children less than 4 years;Adult;Pregnant or lactating women;Seniors	<i>Escherichia coli</i> VTEC, unspecified; <i>Listeria</i> ; <i>Salmonella</i> ; <i>Staphylococcus - S. aureus</i>	Pork, sausages, poultry, fish/seafood
[6, 7]	children up to 14 years old	<i>Escherichia coli</i> , pathogenic, VTEC	Dairy
[8]	Infant or toddler;Adult;Elderly	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	Pork, sausages,dairy
[2, 9, 10]	General population	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	Fish/Seafood
[11]	General population	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	Sausages, fish/seafood, unspecified meat, paté, dairy
[12]	General population	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	Pork, sausages, unspecified meat
[13]	Men;Seniors;Women	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	Fruiting vegetables
[14]	General population	<i>Salmonella</i>	Pork
[15]	Children less than 4 years;Infant or toddler;Adult;Seniors	<i>Salmonella</i>	Dairy
[16]	does not apply to this study	<i>Salmonella</i>	Eggs and egg products
[17]	General population	<i>Taenia solium</i>	Pork

4. Hazard identification

Thirteen different hazards were included in the QMRA, from which 9 bacteria, 2 parasites and 2 viruses. The most frequent hazards included in QMRA studies were *Listeria* (n=7), *Escherichia coli* (n=6), *Salmonella* (n=5) and *Campylobacter* (n=4) (Figure 2 and Table 4).

Figure 2: Number of types QMRA per hazard

5. Food products included in the QMRAs

The majority of the QMRA included food products of animal origin, mainly pork meat (n=6), poultry (n=6), sausages with several types of meat possible (n=4) and dairy products (n=4). Only one study considered

fruits and vegetables products. Nine studies included more than one type of food in their QMRA (Figure 3 and Table 4).

Figure 3 : Type of products considered in the QMRA

6. Objectives of the QMRAs

Several objectives of the QMRA studies were identified. The evaluation of illness risk was the major objective (n=9), followed by intervention assessment (n=7), exposure assessment (n=6) and process assessment (n=5). Risk ranking (n=3) and evaluation of exposure via different pathways (n=1) were also cited as the main objective of the QMRA (Table 5).

39% of the QMRA studies had two or more different objectives.

Table 5: Objectives of the QMRA

Objective	Number of QMRAs
Evaluation of illness risk	9
Interventions	7
Exposure assessment	6
Process assessment	5
Risk ranking	3
Evaluation of exposure via different pathways	1

7. Start and end steps included in the QMRA

QMRA studies had several start points as shown in the Figure 4. It could start at the primary production step (n=6), slaughterhouse (n=4), distribution (n=4), processing step (n=3) or at the consumer stage (n=1). A less number of end points steps were declared and the main end point was the consumer stage step (n=15).

Figure 4: Start and End points steps included in the QMRA (n: corresponds to the number of studies)

8. Data and models

8.1. Data sources

Three sources of data were identified: own data (n=13), from the literature (n=16) and from a scientific network (n=4).

From the 19 entries of the questionnaire, 9 responded to the question: “Are you willing to publicly share those data in raw?” Only one participant does not want to share data in raw and no respondents reported having a database of their own.

8.2. Dose-response models

14 QMRA studies included dose-response models:

- *Listeria monocytogenes*: Dose-response from Pouillot et al.(2015); FAO/WHO 2004; Rose et al., 1991; EFSA BIOHAZ Panel (2018) using the approach described in Pouillot et al.(2015)
- *E. coli* VTEC : Perrin et al. 2015
- *Salmonella*: FAO/WHO 2002 and Teunis et al. 2010
- *Campylobacter* : Teunis and Havelaar 2000 and Nauta et al 2009

9. Feedback of the questionnaire

Current March 2021, two different emails requesting the feedback of the questionnaire were sent to the members who answered to the survey (n=9) and to those who open the questionnaire but did not take action to respond (n=9).

9.1. Responses from the contacts that responded to the survey

For those who filled the questionnaire, three questions were asked:

1. What level of effort did you provide to complete the survey? From 1 (none) to 10 (extreme)
2. Can you tell us what constrained you the most?
3. Do you have any other comments or suggestions regarding the survey?

Only three participants responded to the email. The mean level of effort to complete the questionnaire was 3/10. The main constrains cited were the amount of the time to fill the questionnaire, the lack of knowledge due to the risk assessment work that was on going and the quantity of data to be filled in.

Regarding the comments or recommendations, a participant suggested to extend to chemical risk assessment (but it was not included in the scope of the questionnaire) and a question on whether attention is given to variability and uncertainty in the QMRA model was missing for another participant.

9.2. Responses from the contacts who opened the questionnaire but did not responded

The contact persons who opened the questionnaire but did not responded were contacted again in order to retrieve the reason why (e.g., forgetfulness, lack of time, lack of QMRA studies, questions that are too constraining, ...). Two contacts who responded in return, stated that they did not perform QMRA. One contact person got interrupted and at the end did not completed the questionnaire and for one contact the questionnaire was not relevant to complete.

C. Analysis of the data and model quality and accessibility

Risk assessors need to use high quality data but some don't have the ability or the time requested to generate its own. The sharing of data and meta-data currently used in quantitative microbial risk assessment (QMRA) could be of help for risk assessors in future risk assessment studies. As a result also food safety would benefit if high quality (meta-) data was easily accessible. In this section, the criteria to evaluate the quality of the (meta-) data and to increase their accessibility will be discussed.

1. Criteria for data and model quality

Quality of data is a very important point in the confidence of QRA outputs. The assessment of data and model quality is a specific task of QRA. A recent document from FAO and WHO entitled "Microbiological risk assessment: guidance for food" give tools to assess the quality the risk assessment [18].

1.2. Data quality

To validate data, the source and the related study information must be available, independent of one specific model, reusable by other investigators and accessible in a platform such as ComBase [18]. Data may come from the peer-reviewed, which are generally preferable but sometimes less accessible and with restricted information, or non-peer-reviewed literature. The user must specify the strengths and the limitation of the data, method and/or the analysis used [18]. Raw data should be prioritized. The data must be described by statistical tools in order to identify distributions (parametric or non-parametric) by favoring graphical methods rather than statistical tests. Finally, background information of the (meta-) data source is a plus in order to decide on the appropriateness of using the data in a given risk assessment.

1.3. Model quality

To ensure the quality of the data, this latter must be applied and compared to other data sources, data and model sources or projects in progress for microbiological risk assessment. To increase the quality, the model must be verified, calibrated, validated [18].

1.3.1. Verification

Verification consists of checking if the code of the model is well documented and all steps clearly described. Inputs, equations and assumptions should be explicitly stated, also as the limits of the implementation. The propagation of the units of measurement must be ensured and the error in any computational step showed. Finally, the outputs must be evaluated to be realistic. Peer review is also essential for verification [18].

1.3.2. Calibration

The **calibration/anchoring** consists of adjusting the model ensuring that the outputs (e.g. prediction) are compatible with the observed data. The procedure for the calibration/anchoring must be clearly described [18].

1.3.3. Validation

The **validation** step consists of demonstrating the accuracy of the model predictions according to the question, the data used, the input assumptions and the responses of the model. In the WHO report, four steps for the validations are described by Dee [18-20]:

- Conceptual validation: Are the assumptions realistic? (support of experts opinion and experimental or observational data)
- Validation of algorithms: Is the model concept correctly translated in a mathematical manner?
- Validation of software code: Is the code implementation in the software properly transcribed?
- Functional validation: Are the results comparable regarding the observations in the real-world? (e.g. comparison with observations obtained independently, epidemiology)

It must be highlighted that even if the outputs don't match with observational data, it does not mean that the model is wrong. Also, close agreement between the risk-assessment outputs and the observations can be fortuitous [18].

If the comparison with independent data is not possible, validation procedures must include:

- Identification of the major inputs and pathways of the model
- Comparison with outputs from a different model
- Sensitivity analysis of the inputs and the results
- Uncertainty analysis

1.4. Uncertainty and sensitivity analysis

One of the criteria to assess data quality is to assess uncertainty [21]. This corresponds to the lack of knowledge that could be reduced by further studies and additional data [18]. Considering uncertainty from data in the risk estimate, one of the general principles of microbiological risk assessment cited in Codex Alimentarius, is to ensure data quality and precision [22].

Characterization of the uncertainty of each input of a risk model and assessment of their impacts on output is indeed part of the uncertainty analysis formal process. The integration of uncertainty for model output depends on the number of uncertain inputs. Various uncertainty analysis approaches have been proposed by different actors in the field of risk assessment [23-25]. These approaches include useful elements to consider when constructing an appropriate generic uncertainty analysis framework (see Figure 5). Recently ANSES [26] has proposed an iterative approach in five stages, adapted from the one proposed by EFSA [24].

Figure 5: Framework for uncertainty analysis

Quantifiable uncertainty could be included in the quantitative risk assessment and the sources identified. In order to identify the major source of uncertainty, sensitivity analysis can be performed, by observing variations of the outputs, when the uncertain inputs are modified [24]. In the case of non-characterizable uncertainty, such as that provided by the assumptions made all along with the risk quantification model, it must be identified and transcribed, in order to increase transparency and to be taken into consideration by risk managers [18].

1.5. Credibility of the risk assessment data and models

To increase the credibility of the risk assessment data and models, it is recommended to fully document the risk assessment procedure (e.g. data and data sources, data analysis, scenarios applied, comparison with alternative model formulations, justifications of the choices, assumptions, verification of the model quality, etc.) to contribute to transparency and consistency of the risk assessment models [22, 27]. In addition, peer-review increases credibility [18].

2. Criteria for data accessibility

Data accessibility is a more recent preoccupation of risk assessors (Plaza-Rodriguez et al 2015). Multiple QMRA studies exist in the literature as listed in recent reviews [28-30] and identified by the survey. However, (meta) data is not always readily available for further studies.

Two criteria will be used to characterize the data used in QRA:

- Are metadata available?
- Are the data available in an open format / open platform?

Metadata is of interest in the field of QRA. It is defined as structured information that allows data to be found and interpreted. The structured and harmonized metadata could assist in a more efficient exchange, re-use and continuous improvement of the models [27].

In order to enable machine-actionability to find, access, interoperate and reuse data with low human intervention, FAIR principles can be applied to a further application on Health Surveillance and One-Health Ontologies. A publication from 2016 describes guidelines and definition of the principles [31] that correspond to:

- **Findable:** data must be findable by humans or computers. To do so, (meta-)data must be assigned with a unique and persistent identifier. Data must be well described/identified and both metadata and data should be properly available in a searchable resource.
- **Accessible:** accessibility of the (meta-)data must be specified and metadata must be accessible even if the data is no longer available
- **Interoperable:** The data must be compatible with different storage and distribution paths such as storage platform. Interoperability must “address the ability of systems and services [...] to have clear, shared expectations for the contents, context and meaning of that data”
- **Reusable:** data must be made available in such a way that it can be used by multiple means and for multiple applications

In the future of One Health, data must also be evolving and reproducible (FAIRER).

Harmonized annotation is therefore an important step for the accessibility, interpretation and reuse of the (meta-)data. The annotation must be done considering controlled and validated vocabularies. Recently, a publication described the Minimum Information Required to Annotate Food Safety Risk Assessment Models (MIRARAM), which proposed guidelines for metadata annotation in a harmonized way [32]. At a minimum, thirteen metadata concepts must be specified for the model and the parameters included:

- model name: name of the model
- model Id: unique identifier
- creation date: date of the creation of the file
- license: rights given for the use of the model
- model execution: information required for model interoperability
- reference description: resource such as DOI or URL where the model has been described
- model scope: general description and application of the model
- parameter ID: unique identifier of the parameter
- parameter classification: classification of the parameter as input, constant or output
- parameter unit: unit of the parameter (e.g. log reduction, risk proportion)
- parameter data type: type of format of the data
- parameter default value

Two metadata standards commonly used to describe research data are Dublin Core and the Data Documentation Initiative [33, 34].

Finally, dedicated platform with clear procedures, easy to use, identified and validated by several partners improve the accessibility to the (meta-)data and models [27]. Beyond the resources made available, it is necessary to mobilize the viability of the tools through the participation of contributors (providing knowledge) and users of data and models (e.g. risk assessors, risk managers, researchers).

3. Quality and accessibility of the data and models identified by the survey

The quality and accessibility of the data and models of the survey were assessed by checking several points that must be considered (Table 6).

To assess quality, ten check points were verified:

- Raw data available in the publication or in the appendix
- Data sources indicated in the text
- Equations reported in the text
- Inputs listed in the text or in a table
- Assumptions clearly described in the text or in a table
- Identification of the major pathways of contamination
- Uncertainty and/or sensitivity analysis
- Validation of the model (e.g. comparison with epidemiological estimation or other values)
- Software used for QMRA indicated
- Code/simulation document available

To assess accessibility three points were checked:

- Publication publicly available
- At least one database easily accessible cited
- QMRA model and/or (meta-) data available in a platform

4. Identification of existing European initiatives contributing to improve exchange and interoperability of knowledge

These recent years, several European initiatives focused on the identification and creation of tools and codified procedures to support accessibility and exchange of knowledge and resources for future QRAs. There has been an increasing interest for One Health Surveillance harmonization effort. International agencies such as EFSA and ECDC developed tools and supported projects in order to promote exchange and interoperability of knowledge as listed in Figure 6.

4.1.1. One health surveillance Initiative on harmonization of data collection and interpretation (ORION) project

ORION project is a Joint Integrative Project part of the One Health EJP program. This project aimed to “establishing and strengthening inter-institutional collaboration and transdisciplinary knowledge transfer in the area of One Health Surveillance (OHS) data integration and interpretation” [35]. In this context, a codex document was created, structured in four principles : the collaboration, the knowledge, the data and the dissemination principles [35]. More specifically, the data principle aimed to support OHS data interoperability, integration and interpretation by providing tools and guidelines to annotate surveillance (meta-)data. FAIR principles were considered with a focus on semantic interoperability, which means to ensure integrity and meaning of the data considered by humans and by machines, through the definition of common vocabularies. As part of this project, the Health Surveillance Ontology was developed and is publicly available: <https://w3id.org/hso>.

To annotate data using Health Surveillance Ontology, the members of the ORION project, in collaboration with other projects, developed a tool for semantic annotation of data in Excel (ExcelRDF plug-in) and convert the data in Resource Description Framework (RDF) format, which is a standard model for data interchange on the Web [35]. This tool is included in the [One Health Linked Data Toolbox \(OHLDT\)](#). OHLDT gather the required web applications based on HSO in the context of surveillance data in order to facilitate accessibility and interoperability of data across sectors [36].

Table 6: Quality and accessibility assessment of the studies identified in the survey

Réf.	Quality											Accessibility		
	Raw data available	Data sources	Equations	Inputs described	Assumptions described	Adjustements	Identification of the major pathways of contamination	Uncertainty (U) or/and sensitivity (S) analysis	Validation procedures (e.g. comparison)	Software indicated	Code/simulation document available	Publication available	Open database cited	Elements in a platform
[17]	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓ S	✓	✓	x	✓	✓	x
University of Cordoba (in progress)	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓ S	x	✓	x	x	x	x
[5]	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	x	✓	✓ S	✓	✓	x	✓	x	x
[4]	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	x	✓	✓ U	x	✓	x	✓	✓	x
[14]	x	✓	✓	✓	x	x	✓	✓ U	✓	✓	x	✓	✓	x
[8]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	x	✓	✓ S	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
[1]	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓ U	✓	✓	x	✓	✓	x
Food Safety Authority of Ireland (in progress)	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	x
[15]	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	x	✓	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
[6, 7]	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	x	✓	x	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
[2]	x	✓	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	x	x	✓	x	✓	✓	x
[2]	x	✓	✓	✓	x	x	✓	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x
[2, 9, 10]	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓ S	✓	✓	x	✓	✓	x
[16]	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	x	✓ S	x	✓	x	✓	x	x
[11]	x	✓	✓	✓	x	x	x	✓ U	x	✓	x	✓	✓	x
[12]	✓	✓	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓ U+S	✓	✓	x	✓	✓	x
[3]	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	x	✓ U+S	✓	✓	x	✓	✓	x
[13]	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓ U	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

4.1.2. One Health Structure In Europe Surveillance data (COHESIVE) project

The Joint Integrative Project COHESIVE of the One Health EJP program aims to promote the collaboration between human and veterinary risk-analysis of zoonosis in Europe. One of the tasks was to identify existing resources for risk analysis and epidemiology valuable in the One Health approach. An open source platform was designed to collect and analyze surveillance and outbreak data in the case of foodborne zoonosis [37]. Tools for tracing were intended to be settled up, with whole genome sequencing (WGS) information and risk assessment models (<http://cohesive.onehealth.ejp.eu/>). Focus was made on the interoperability of the data exchange, by the mean of standardized and harmonized procedures [38].

4.1.3. RaDAR: Risk and Disease burden of Antimicrobial Resistance

The Joint Research Program RaDAR aimed “to generate consensus estimates for sources attribution, risks of exposure and disease burden of AMR by integrating available data from various sources” [39]. As part of this project, databases collection of field genomics and metagenomics data were performed for several hazards and animal or human population and RAKIP principles were used to assess and exchange for harmonized models [40].

The RaDAR model inventory web application was then developed to allow to share models and information, and users can “create, read, edit, write, execute and compile FSKX files within the web browser”. This later can be assessed in the following link: <http://ejp-radar.eu/> [41].

4.1.4. DiSCoVer: Discovering the sources of Salmonella, Campylobacter, VTEC and antimicrobial resistance

Discovering the sources of *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter*, VTEC and antimicrobial resistance (DiSCoVer) project is a Joint Research Project that aim to identify gaps (knowledge, methodological and data) for source attribution of zoonotic pathogens and antimicrobial resistance determinants. Within the framework of this project, a systematic search of available data should be carried out, which can be a source with undeniable importance, notably in the integration of AMR data into source attribution and risk assessment approaches [42].

4.1.5. NOVA: Novel approaches for design and evaluation of cost-effective surveillance across the food chain

NOVA project is a Joint Research Project part of the One Health EJP program. This project aimed to “develop new surveillance tools and methods and to harmonize and optimize the use of existing surveillance system data” [43].

One of the task was to make an inventory of the data sources with the assessment of availability, quality and fitness for data-driven surveillance. This inventory helped to visualize the coverage of the surveillance system.

4.2. Examples of platforms improving the share and exchange of knowledge

4.2.1. Risk Assessment Modelling and Knowledge Integration Platforms (RAKIP)

RAKIP project is a joint project of three European institutions (ANSES, BfR and DTU Food). The goal is to support modelers, risk assessors and risk managers but also research scientists by providing a source of reliable knowledge and to improve the sharing of models and data. This project aims to build resources to exchange knowledge (models and data) on a common platform (RAKIP Web Portal) with harmonized data formats (the Food Safety Knowledge Exchange: FSKX Format) and annotation rules, from which the MIRARAM principles are derived.

A model repository is available at the website <https://knime.bfr.berlin/landingpage>, where users can choose the desired models and data by filtering according to the desired software, environment (e.g.

food type), the hazard and the type of data or models (e.g. generic model, dose-response model, datasets...). This platform allows to visualize metadata and model information, to download the set in FSKX format, which can be retrieved by a zip document extraction software. Finally, this portal also enables to run the models and to change input settings to perform simulations.

Detailed information about RAKIP project and the associated Web Portal can be found in the following website: <https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/rakip-web-portal/>

4.2.2. The EFSA Comprehensive European Food Consumption Database

EFSA provides a European Food Consumption Database where detailed dietary data in the European countries is available to improve the accessibility in the context of exposure and risk assessment work. These can be found in the following link for survey detail and for chronic and acute food consumption statistics: [The EFSA Comprehensive European Food Consumption Database | European Food Safety Authority \(europa.eu\)](#)

4.2.3. European Surveillance System (TESSy)

ECDC has set up a platform for the collection, analysis and dissemination of surveillance data of infectious diseases, ([The European Surveillance System \(TESSy\)](#)), which is gradually being shifted by the EpiPulse platform which included also the five [Epidemic Intelligence Information System \(EPIS\)](#) platforms and the [Threat Tracking Tool \(TTT\)](#).

The TESSy platform allows the access to aggregated data without restriction by the “[Surveillance Atlas of Infectious Diseases](#)” tool. However, the access of subsets data and the publication are also available by requesting the access.

D. Ressources to perform QMRA

As seen previously, there are existing databases and repository platforms, allowing to access to high quality data and risk assessment models. Figure 6 gives an overview, with a non-exhaustive list of data and model sources or projects in progress for microbiological risk assessment.

Figure 6 : Data and model sources or projects in progress for microbiological risk assessment (non-exhaustive list)

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E. Appendix

Appendix 1 : Survey form

Cross-sectoral framework for quality Assurance Resources for countries in the European Union – CARE

Objectives of WP4

- To investigate and benchmark the availability and quality of data commonly used for human risk assessments among OHEJP partners, and describe any constraints for making them more easily accessible.
 - To promote national participation in initiatives from EU authorities that serve to make high quality data more readily available for human risk assessments.
 - For the two bullet points above, to have an early and close coordination with existing data collection initiatives such as EFSA's SIGMA project.
- One of the tasks in WP4, which is dealing with (meta-) data, of the EJP-Care project is to develop and launch a survey among OHEJP members and broader to identify which data is currently used in human risk assessment.

Previous

Next

Who are you ? (mandatory)

Question 1: Name of Institut / Agency / Organization

Question 2: First name and Last name of the scientist

Question 3: Email adress

Question 4: Position

Question 5: Date of questionnaire filling

Survey on Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment Models

Question 6: Title of the study (mandatory)

Question 7: What were the objectives of your study? (mandatory)

- | | |
|---|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Evaluation of illness risk | <input type="checkbox"/> Process assessment |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Evaluation of illness risk following outbreak | <input type="checkbox"/> Risk ranking |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Exposure assessment | <input type="checkbox"/> Assessment impact of performant objective and microbiological criteria |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Health burden assessment | <input type="checkbox"/> Interventions |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Interventions (assessment impact of performant objective, microbiological criteria, ...) | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |

If 'other', can you precise ?

Question 8: Which country was included? (mandatory)

Question 9: Hazard(s): define as precisely as possible: e.g. STEC O157, Campylobacter spec., Campylobacter jejuni, Salmonella Tyhimurium (mandatory)

Adenovirus
Aeromonas
Aeromonas caviae
Aeromonas hydrophila
Aeromonas spp., unspecified
Aeromonas veronii
Aichi virus
Anisakis
Anisakis simplex
Anisakis spp., unspecified
Astrovirus
Avastrovirus
Bacillus
Bacillus anthracis
Bacillus cereus
Bacillus cereus toxins
Balantidium
Balantidium coli
Balantidium spp., unspecified
Biogenic amines
Bovine enterovirus
Brucella
Brucella - B. abortus
Brucella - B. canis
Brucella - B. ceti
Brucella - B. melitensis
Brucella - B. noetomae
Brucella - B. ovis
Brucella - B. pinnipedialis
Brucella - B. suis
Brucella spp., unspecified
Calicivirus
Campylobacter
Campylobacter - C. pylori
Campylobacter coli
Campylobacter cryaerophilus
Campylobacter curvus
Campylobacter fetus
Campylobacter fetus subsp. fetus

Campylobacter fetus subsp. venerealis
Campylobacter gracilis
Campylobacter hominis
Campylobacter hyointestinalis
Campylobacter hyointestinalis subsp. hyointestinalis
Campylobacter hyointestinalis subsp. lawsonii
Campylobacter jejuni
Campylobacter jejuni subsp. doylei
Campylobacter jejuni subsp. jejuni
Campylobacter lari
Campylobacter mucosalis
Campylobacter pylori subsp. mustelae
Campylobacter rectus
Campylobacter spp., unspecified
Campylobacter sputorum
Campylobacter sputorum subsp. bubulus
Campylobacter sputorum subsp. mucosalis
Campylobacter sputorum subsp. sputorum
Campylobacter upsaliensis
Cestodes
Clostridium
Clostridium - C. botulinum
Clostridium - C. difficile
Clostridium perfringens
Clostridium spp., unspecified
Coxiella
Coxiella burnetii
Coxiella popilliae
Coxiella spp., unspecified
Cronobacter
Cronobacter sakazakii
Cronobacter spp., unspecified
Cryptosporidium
Cryptosporidium parvum
Cryptosporidium spp., unspecified
Cyclospora
Cyclospora cayetanensis
Cyclospora spp., unspecified
Cysticerci
Cysticerci of Taenia saginata

Cysticerci of Taenia solium
Cysticerci spp., unspecified
Diphyllobothrium
Diphyllobothrium latum
Duvenhage virus
Echinococcus
Echinococcus granulosus
Echinococcus multilocularis
Echinococcus oligarthrus
Echinococcus spp., unspecified
Enterococcus
Enterococcus spp., unspecified
Enterococcus faecalis
Enterococcus faecium
Enterococcus, pathogenic
Enterococcus, pathogenic - E. faecalis
Enterococcus, pathogenic - E. faecium
Enterococcus, pathogenic - Enterococcus spp., unspecified
Enteroinvasive E. coli (EIEC)
Enteropathogenic E. coli (EPEC)
Enterotoxigenic E. coli (ETEC)
Enterohemorrhagic E. coli (EHEC)
Enterovirus
Erysipelothrix
Erysipelothrix rhusiopathiae
Erysipelothrix spp., unspecified
Escherichia coli
Escherichia coli VTEC, unspecified
Escherichia coli VTEC, unspecified1
Escherichia coli, non-pathogenic
Escherichia coli, non-pathogenic, unspecified
Escherichia coli, pathogenic
Escherichia coli, pathogenic1
Escherichia coli, pathogenic - Verotoxigenic E. coli (VTEC) - VTEC O75:H5
Escherichia coli, pathogenic, unspecified
Escherichia coli, pathogenic, VTEC
Flavivirus
Flavivirus dengue virus
Flavivirus Japanese encephalitis virus
Flavivirus Kyasanur forest disease virus

Flavivirus Langat virus
Flavivirus Louping ill virus
Flavivirus Omsk haemorrhagic fever virus
Flavivirus Powassan virus
Flavivirus St. Louis encephalitis virus
Flavivirus tick borne encephalitis virus (Eastern)
Flavivirus tick borne encephalitis virus (Greek goat)
Flavivirus tick borne encephalitis virus (Turkish sheep)
Flavivirus tick borne encephalitis virus (Western)
Flavivirus West Nile virus
Flavivirus yellow fever virus
Flavivirus, unspecified
Foodborne viruses
Francisella
Francisella philomiragia
Francisella spp., unspecified
Francisella tularensis
Fungi
Giardia
Giardia intestinalis (lamblia)
Giardia spp., unspecified
Hantavirus
Hepatitis A virus
Hepatitis E virus
Hepatitis virus
Histamine
Leptospira
Leptospira borgpetersenii
Leptospira interrogans
Leptospira interrogans serovar Icterohaemorrhagiae
Leptospira interrogans serovar Saxkoebing
Leptospira interrogans serovar Sejroe
Leptospira kirschneriae
Leptospira spp., unspecified
Listeria
Listeria - L. grayi
Listeria ivanovii
Listeria monocytogenes
Listeria seeligeri
Listeria spp., unspecified

Listeria welshimeri
Mamastrovirus
Microsporium
Microsporium canis
Mycobacterium
Mycobacterium - M. avium complex
Mycobacterium - M. avium complex - M. avium subsp. avium
Mycobacterium - M. avium complex - M. avium subsp. hominissuis
Mycobacterium - M. bovis
Mycobacterium - M. microti
Mycobacterium - M. pinnipedii
Mycobacterium africanum
Mycobacterium avium
Mycobacterium avium subsp. avium
Mycobacterium avium subsp. paratuberculosis
Mycobacterium avium subsp. silvaticum
Mycobacterium caprae
Mycobacterium celatum
Mycobacterium fortuitum
Mycobacterium intracellulare
Mycobacterium kansasii
Mycobacterium scrofulaceum
Mycobacterium spp., unspecified
Mycobacterium tuberculosis
Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex
Mycobacterium xenopi
Mycobacterium, atypical
Nairovirus
Nairovirus Crimean Congo haemorrhagic fever virus
Nairovirus spp., unidentified
Nematodes
Neorickettsia
Neorickettsia risticii
norovirus (Norwalk-like virus)
Parasites
Plesiomonas
Plesiomonas shigelloides
Plesiomonas spp., unspecified
Protozoa
Rotavirus

Rotavirus1
Salmonella
Salmonella - Not typeable
Salmonella - Other serovars
Salmonella - S. Typhimurium, monophasic
Salmonella Dublin
Salmonella enterica, monophasic
Salmonella Enteritidis
Salmonella Typhi
Salmonella Typhimurium
Salmonella Virchow
sapovirus (Sapparo-like virus)
Sarcocystis
Sarcocystis hominis
Sarcocystis spp., unspecified
Sarcocystis suihominis
Shigella
Shigella boydii
Shigella dysenteriae
Shigella flexneri
Shigella sonnei
Shigella spp., unspecified
Staphylococcal enterotoxins
Staphylococcal enterotoxins - Enterotoxin A
Staphylococcal enterotoxins - Enterotoxin B
Staphylococcal enterotoxins - Enterotoxin C
Staphylococcal enterotoxins - Enterotoxin D
Staphylococcal enterotoxins - Enterotoxin E
Staphylococcal enterotoxins - Enterotoxin H
Staphylococcal enterotoxins - Enterotoxin, unspecified
Staphylococcus
Staphylococcus - S. aureus
Staphylococcus - S. aureus, methicillin resistant (MRSA)
Staphylococcus - S. pseudintermedius, methicillin resistant (MRSP)
Staphylococcus enterotoxins
Staphylococcus intermedius
Staphylococcus spp., unspecified
Streptococcus suis
Streptococcus equi subsp. zooepidemicus
Streptococcus

Streptococcus spp., unspecified
Strongyloide spp., unspecified
Strongyloides
Strongyloides stercoralis
Thermophilic Campylobacter spp., unspecified
Tick-borne encephalitis virus (TBE)
toxigenic V. cholerae
toxigenic V. parahaemolyticus
Toxocara
Toxocara canis
Toxocara spp., unspecified
Toxoplasma
Toxoplasma gondii
Toxoplasma spp., unspecified
Trichinella
Trichinella britovi
Trichinella nativa
Trichinella pseudospiralis
Trichinella spiralis
Trichinella spp., unspecified
Trichinella T6
Trichophyton
Trichophyton mentagrophytes
Trichophyton spp., unspecified
Trichophyton verrucosum
Unspecified Lyssavirus
Unspecified Microsporum
Vesiculovirus
Vesiculovirus Chandipura virus
Vesiculovirus spp., unidentified
Vesiculovirus Vesicular stomatitis virus
Vibrio
Vibrio - V. cholerae
Vibrio - V. parahaemolyticus
Vibrio spp., unspecified
Vibrio vulnificus
Viruses
Yersinia
Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 1A
Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 1B

Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 1B-O:13
Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 1B-O:21
Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 1B-O:7
Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 1B-O:8
Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 2
Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 2-O:5,27
Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 2-O:9
Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 3
Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 3-O:3
Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 3-O:5,27
Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 4
Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 4-O:3
Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 5
Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 5-O:1,2,3
Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 5-O:2,3
Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 5-O:3
Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - O:1,2,3
Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - O:13
Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - O:21
Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - O:7
Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - O:8
Yersinia enterocolitica
Yersinia enterocolitica non typable
Yersinia enterocolitica O:1
Yersinia enterocolitica O:2,3
Yersinia enterocolitica O:3
Yersinia enterocolitica O:5
Yersinia enterocolitica O:5,27
Yersinia enterocolitica O:6
Yersinia enterocolitica O:9
Yersinia enterocolitica unspecified
Yersinia frederiksenii
Yersinia intermedia
Yersinia kristensenii
Yersinia molaretti
Yersinia pseudotuberculosis
Yersinia spp., unspecified
Other

If 'Other', can you precise?

Question 10: Product: define as precisely as possible, including the animal species in case of meat. Ground pork meat, ground beef meat, filet americain, salad, red fruits, ...

Alcoholic beverages
Amphibians and Reptiles
Animal fats and oils (processed fat from animal tissue)
Animal other organs (edible offals non-muscle)
Barbecue or steak sauces
Berries and small fruits, PROCESS=Freezing
Berries and small fruits, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Bovine muscle
Bovine, minced meat, USE=Intended to be eaten cooked, PROCESS=Freezing
Bovine, minced meat, USE=Intended to be eaten cooked, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Bovine, minced meat, USE=Intended to be eaten raw, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Bovine, minced meat, USE=Intended to be eaten raw, PROCESS=Freezing
Bread and similar products
Brined cheese (feta-type and similar)
Bulb vegetables, PROCESS=Freezing
Bulb vegetables, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Butter
Buttermilk, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Buttermilk, PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation)
Canned anchovies
Canned herring
Canned mackerel
Canned salmon
Canned sardines
Canned seafood
Canned sprats
Canned tunas and similar
Canned-tinned meat
Cereal doughs -based products
Cereal grains and similar and primary derivatives thereof
Chicken fresh meat
Chicken fresh meat, PROCESS=Freezing
Chicken fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Citrus fruits, PROCESS=Freezing
Citrus fruits, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Cods, hakes, haddocks
Cods, hakes, haddocks, PROCESS=Freezing
Cods, hakes, haddocks, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Composite dishes

Compote of fruit / vegetables
Confectionery including chocolate
Conserve (Composite dishes, PROCESS=Statical sterilisation (in batch or package), PROCESS=Canning / jarring)
Continental european brown cooked sauce, gravy
Cooked cured or seasoned bovine meat
Cooked cured or seasoned pork meat
Cooked cured or seasoned poultry meat
Cooked sausages
Cow milk, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Cow milk,PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation)
Cow milk,PROCESS=UHT
Crabs, sea-spiders
Crabs, sea-spiders, PROCESS=Freezing
Crabs, sea-spiders, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Cream and cream products, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Cream and cream products, PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation)
Cured pork fat (ex lardon)
Cured ripened raw sausages
Cured seasoned bovine meat
Cured seasoned pork meat
Cured unripened raw sausages
Dairy fats
Dairy imitates
Deer fresh meat
Deer fresh meat, PROCESS=Freezing
Deer fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Dessert sauces/toppings
Diadromous fish
Diadromous fish, PROCESS=Freezing
Diadromous fishPROCESS=Unprocessed
Dried fish
Dried seafood
drinking water
Duck fresh meat
Duck fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Eggs and egg products
Equine muscle
Equine muscle, PROCESS=Freezing
Equine muscle, PROCESS=Unprocessed

Extra hard cheese (parmesan, grana type), PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation), SOURCE=Sheep for milk production

Extra hard cheese (parmesan, grana type), PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment, SOURCE=Dairy cows

Extracts of plant origin

Fat emulsions and blended fats

Fine bakery wares

Firm/semi-hard cheese (gouda and edam type), PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment, SOURCE=Sheep for milk production

Firm/semi-hard cheese (gouda and edam type), PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment, SOURCE=Dairy cows

Firm/semi-hard cheese (gouda and edam type), PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment, SOURCE=Goat for milk production

Firm/semi-hard cheese (gouda and edam type), PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation), SOURCE=Sheep for milk production

Firm/semi-hard cheese (gouda and edam type), PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation), SOURCE=Dairy cows

Firm/semi-hard cheese (gouda and edam type), PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation), SOURCE=Goat for milk production

Firm-ripened bloomy (white mould) or washed rind cheese, PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation), SOURCE=Goat for milk production

Firm-ripened bloomy (white mould) or washed rind cheese, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment, SOURCE=Sheep for milk production

Firm-ripened blue mould-veined cheese, PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation), SOURCE=Dairy cows

Firm-ripened blue mould-veined cheese, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment, SOURCE=Goat for milk production

Firm-ripened cheese with added herbs, spices or other ingredients

Fish meat and products thereof

Flounders, halibuts, soles

Flounders, halibuts, soles¹

Flounders, halibuts, soles, PROCESS=Unprocessed

Flowering brassica, PROCESS=Freezing

Flowering brassica,PROCESS=Unprocessed

Foie gras

Food for particular diets

Food products for young population

Fresh raw sausages, SOURCE=Bovinae (bovines)

Fresh raw sausages, SOURCE=Generic poultry

Fresh raw sausages, SOURCE=Pig

Fresh uncured cheese

Freshwater crustaceans

Freshwater crustaceans, PROCESS=Freezing

Freshwater crustaceans, PROCESS=Unprocessed

Freshwater fish
Freshwater fish, PROCESS=Freezing
Freshwater fish, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Fruit / vegetable juices and nectars, PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation)
Fruit / vegetable juices and nectars,PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Fruit / vegetable spreads and similar
Fruit and primary derivatives thereof
Fruit or fruit-vegetable puree
Fruit preparations for fillings and/or flavouring
Fruit/vegetable juice concentrate
Fruit/vegetable juice powder
Fruit/vegetables/plant drinks, spreads and related products
Fruiting vegetables, PROCESS=Freezing
Fruiting vegetables, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Fungi, PROCESS=Freezing
Fungi, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Game birds fresh meat
Garden vegetables and primary derivatives thereof
Goat milk, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Goat milk, PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation)
Goat milk, PROCESS=UHT
Goat muscle
Goat muscle, PROCESS=Freezing
Goat muscle, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Goose fresh meat
Goose fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Goose liver
Guinea-fowl fresh meat
Guinea-fowl fresh meatPROCESS=Freezing
Guinea-fowl fresh meatPROCESS=Unprocessed
Hard cheese (cheddar, emmental type), PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation), SOURCE=Sheep for milk production
Hard cheese (cheddar, emmental type), PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation), SOURCE=Dairy cows
Hard cheese (cheddar, emmental type), PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation), SOURCE=Goat for milk production
Hard cheese (cheddar, emmental type), PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment, SOURCE=Sheep for milk production
Hard cheese (cheddar, emmental type), PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment, SOURCE=Dairy cows
Hard cheese (cheddar, emmental type), PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment, SOURCE=Goat for milk production
Hen eggs

Herbs, spices and similar
Herbs/spices sauces
Herrings, sardines, anchovies
Herrings, sardines, anchovies, PROCESS=Freezing
Herrings, sardines, anchovies, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Honey
Infant and follow-on formulae
Ingredients for hot drinks and infusions
Insects and arachnids (including species only consumed outside EU)
Isolated purified ingredients (including mineral or synthetic)
Jam, apricots
Jam, blackberries
Jam, blueberries
Jam, cranberries
Jam, currants (black)
Jam, currants (red)
Jam, gooseberries
Jam, lingonberry
Jam, mandarins
Jam, mixed fruit
Jam, oranges
Jam, peaches
Jam, plums
Jam, raspberries
Jam, rose hips
Jam, sour cherry
Jam, strawberries
Jam, sweet cherry
Juice, apple, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, apricot, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, beetroot, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, black currant, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, blackberry, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, carrot, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, celery, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, citrus, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, cranberry, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, cucumber, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, elderberry, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, grape, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment

Juice, grapefruit, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, guava, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, lemon, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, lime, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, mango, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, nectarine, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, orange, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, passion fruit, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, peach, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, pear, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, pineapple, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, pomegranate, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, potato, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, prune, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, red currant, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, tomato, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, turnip, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Juice, white cabbage, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Lamb fresh meat, PROCESS=Freezing
Lamb fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Leafy vegetables, PROCESS=Freezing
Leafy vegetables, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Legume seeds and primary derivatives thereof
Legumes with pod, PROCESS=Freezing
Legumes with pod, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Liquid or gel separated from plant RPCs
Liver-type sausage
Lobsters, spiny-rock lobster
Lobsters, spiny-rock lobster, PROCESS=Freezing
Lobsters, spiny-rock lobster, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Mammals and birds meat and products thereof
Mammals kidney
Mammals liver
Margarines and similar
Marinated / pickled fish
Marinated / pickled seafood
Marinated meat
Marine fishes not identified
Marine fishes not identified, PROCESS=Freezing
Marine fishes not identified, PROCESS=Unprocessed

Marmalade
Mayonnaise, hollandaise and related sauces
Meat and dairy imitates
Meat imitates
Meat specialties
Milk and dairy concentrate
Milk and dairy powders
Milk and milk products (dairy)
Miscellaneous coastal marine fishes
Miscellaneous coastal marine fishes, PROCESS=Freezing
Miscellaneous coastal marine fishes, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Miscellaneous demersal marine fishes, PROCESS=Freezing
Miscellaneous demersal marine fishes, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Miscellaneous fruits (generic), PROCESS=Freezing
Miscellaneous fruits (generic), PROCESS=Unprocessed
Miscellaneous pelagic marine fishes
Miscellaneous pelagic marine fishes, PROCESS=Freezing
Miscellaneous pelagic marine fishes, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Mixed fruit and vegetable juices, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Mixed fruit juice, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Mixed fruit nectars, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Mixed juices with added ingredients, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Mixed vegetable juice, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Molluscs, SOURCE=Bivalvia - Clams, etc. (generic)
Mustard and related sauces
Nectar, apple, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Nectar, apricot, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Nectar, banana, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Nectar, mango, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Nectar, orange, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Nectar, peach, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Nectar, pear, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Nectar, pineapple, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Nuts and primary derivatives thereof
Oilseeds and oilfruits
Ovine milk, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment
Ovine milk, PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation)
Ovine milk, PROCESS=UHT
Partridge fresh meat
Partridge fresh meat, PROCESS=Freezing

Partridge fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Pasta and similar products
Pastas and rice (or other cereal) –based dishes
Pheasant fresh meat
Pheasant fresh meat, PROCESS=Freezing
Pheasant fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Pig muscle
Pig muscle, PROCESS=Freezing
Pig muscle, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Pigeon fresh meat
Pigeon fresh meat, PROCESS=Freezing
Pigeon fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Plants where the vegetative tissue is used as food, PROCESS=Freezing
Plants where the vegetative tissue is used as food, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Pome fruits, PROCESS=Freezing
Pome fruits, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Poultry kidney
Poultry liver
Processed cereal-based food for infants and young children
Processed or preserved fruits
Processed or preserved vegetables and similar
Quail fresh meat
Quail fresh meat, PROCESS=Freezing
Quail fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Rabbit fresh meat
Rabbit fresh meat, PROCESS=Freezing
Rabbit fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Ratites fresh meat
Ratites fresh meat, PROCESS=Freezing
Ratites fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Ready-to-eat meal for infants and young children
Root and tuber vegetables (excluding starchy- and sugar-), PROCESS=Freezing
Root and tuber vegetables (excluding starchy- and sugar-), PROCESS=Unprocessed
Salad dressing
Salads
Salt
Salted seafood
Salt-preserved fish
Sandwich and sandwich-like dishes
Sauces from fermented/hydrolised sources and similar

Savoury extracts and sauce ingredients
Sea urchins and other echinoderms
Seafood and products thereof
Seasoning mixes
Seasoning, sauces and condiments
Sharks, rays, chimaeras
Sharks, rays, chimaeras, PROCESS=Freezing
Sharks, rays, chimaeras, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Sheep (adult) fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Sheep (adult) fresh meat, PROCESS=Freezing
Sheep muscle
Shrimps and prawns
Shrimps and prawns, PROCESS=Freezing
Shrimps and prawns, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Smoked fish
Smoked seafood
Snails
Soft - ripened cheese, =Thermal treatment (heating for preservation), SOURCE=Goat for milk production
Soft - ripened cheese, =Thermal treatment (heating for preservation), SOURCE=Sheep for milk production
Soft - ripened cheese, =Thermal treatment (heating for preservation), SOURCE=Dairy cows
Soft - ripened cheese, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment, SOURCE=Goat for milk production
Soft - ripened cheese, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment, SOURCE=Dairy cows
Soft - ripened cheese, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment, SOURCE=Sheep for milk production
Soups (dry mixture uncooked)
Soups (ready-to-eat)
Spoonable desserts and ice creams
Spoonable desserts and ice creams1
Sprouts, shoots and similar, PROCESS=Freezing
Sprouts, shoots and similar,PROCESS=Unprocessed
Squids, cuttlefishes, octopuses
Starchy roots and tubers
Stems/stalks eaten as vegetables, PROCESS=Freezing
Stems/stalks eaten as vegetables, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Stone fruits, PROCESS=Freezing
Stone fruits, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Structured/textured fish meat products or fish paste
Sugars (mono- and di-saccharides)
Syrups (molasses and other syrups)
Terrestrial animals other than mammals and birds
Tomato ketchup and related sauces

Tomato-containing cooking sauces
Tunas, bonitos, billfishes
Tunas, bonitos, billfishes, PROCESS=Freezing
Tunas, bonitos, billfishes, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Turkey fresh meat
Turkey fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Vegetable fats and oils, edible
Vegetables-based cooked sauce
Vinegar
White sauces
Wild boar fresh meat
Wild boar fresh meat, PROCESS=Freezing
Wild boar fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed
Other

If 'other', can you precise?

Question 11: Who is the target population of the study?

- Infant 0 - 3 months
- Infant 0 - 6 months
- Infant 3 - 6 months
- Infant 6 - 12 months
- Children less than 4 years
- Infant or toddler
- Adult
- Men
- Pregnant or lactating women
- Seniors
- Teenagers
- Women
- Athletes
- Bodybuilders
- Menopausal women
- Weight-reducers
- Other

If 'other', can you precise?

Question 12: Indicate the starting point of model: e.g. farm phase, slaughterhouse, crop collection

- Primary production (farm)
- Processing
- Distribution
- Consumer stage (storage and preparation)
- Slaughterhouse
- Primary production
- Raising
- Other

If 'other', can you precise ?

Question 13a: Which step(s) along the food chain were included? For each step which microbiological processes are modelled?

	Growth	Inactivation
Primary production	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Processing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Distribution	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Consumer stage (storage and preparation)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Primary production	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Processing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Distribution	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Consumer stage (storage and preparation)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Question 13b: If 'other', can you precise ?

Question 14a: Which step(s) along the food chain were included? For each step, which food handling processes are modelled (Choose from: partitioning, mixing, cross-contamination, removal)?

	Joining	Mixing	Partioning	Removal	Cross-contamination
Primary production	<input type="radio"/>				
Slaughterhouse	<input type="radio"/>				
Processing	<input type="radio"/>				
Distribution	<input type="radio"/>				
Consumer stage (storage and preparation)	<input type="radio"/>				
Other	<input type="radio"/>				
Primary production	<input type="radio"/>				
Slaughterhouse	<input type="radio"/>				
Processing	<input type="radio"/>				
Distribution	<input type="radio"/>				
Consumer stage (storage and preparation)	<input type="radio"/>				
Other	<input type="radio"/>				

Question 14b: If 'other', can you precise ?

Question 15: Indicate the final point of model: e.g. end of production, consumer stage, ..

- Processing
- Distribution
- Consumer stage (storage and preparation)
- Slaughterhouse
- Raising
- Other

If 'other', can you precise ?

Question 16: Did you use a deterministic or stochastic approach?

- Stochastic approach
- Deterministic approach
- Other

If 'other', can you precise ?

Question 17a: Did you use a dose-response model ?

- Yes
- No

Question 17b: If 'yes', which one?

Question 18a: Did you perform an evaluation such as a sensitivity or uncertainty analysis?

- Yes
- No

Question 18b: If 'yes', which one ?

Question 19: Which software was used?

- ICRA
- PMM-Lab
- MicroHibro
- R
- @Risk
- FSSP
- FSK-Lab
- Matlab
- Risk ranger
- Swift QMRA
- FDA-iRisk
- Other

If 'other', can you precise ?

Question 20: What kind of output is it? Please be specific and give the dimension of the output: e.g. no. of cfu ingested per person per year, no. of cases per 100,000 persons per year

Question 21a: Is there any publication reference of the QMRA ?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Question 21b: Can you precise the permanent link to the website, doi, article) ?

Question 22: Can you identify the main route(s) or source(s) of contamination?

Question 23a: Did you recommend an intervention strategy to managers?

- Yes
- No

Question 23b: If 'yes', which one?

Question 24: What is the nature of the decision taken by risk manager using QMRA?

- Decree
- Regulation
- Technical instruction
- Communication plan
- Monitoring plan
- No decision
- Don't know
- Other

If 'other', can you precise ?

Question 25a: Publication reference of the riks manager decision?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Question 25b: Publication reference of the riks manager decision?

Data

Question 26a: Did you use any data produced by yourself?

- Yes
- No

Question 26b: If 'yes', which one?

Question 27a: Did you use data from literature?

- Yes No

Question 27b: If 'yes', which one?

Question 28a: Did you use data from a scientific network?

- Yes No

Question 28b: If 'yes', which one?

Question 29a: Which kind of data did you use for hazard identification? (eg. data from outbreak investigations, data related to number of sporadic cases, characteristics of microorganisms throughout the food chain)

Question 29b: Which kind of data did you use for hazard characterisation? (e.g. data from outbreak, from animal models ...)

Question 29c: Which kind of data did you use for exposure assessment : microbiological data ? (e.g. surveillance plan, industry own check results, contamination data (prevalence and concentration), parameters for microbiological and food handling processes: growth (curves), inactivation, cross-contamination, etc.)

Question 29d: Which kind of data did you use for exposure assessment: consumption data ? (e.g. national food consumption database, specific or dedicated survey, ...)

Question 30: Are you willing to publicly share those data in raw?

- Yes No

Question 31: Do you use an own database containing data for Risk Assessment?

- Yes No

Question 32: Are you willing to make this database publicly assessable?

- Yes No

Thank you very much !!!

After receiving the information WP4 members will analyze the outcome of the survey and develop a roadmap for collaboration with (reporting) initiatives (like the SIGMA project, RAKIP etc.) and existing databases maintained by EU authorities (ECDC and EFSA). Furthermore, collaborations will be initiated to establish and strengthen inter-institutional and transdisciplinary knowledge transfers in the area of health data integration.